

Influence of Legal and Regulatory Environment Factor Loan Syndication and Financial Performance of Commercial Banks in Kenya

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Abstract

Scientific literature has shown that loan syndication factors can have an impact on a bank's performance. Good financial performance rewards shareholders for their investing efforts, which pushes them to invest more and allows for economic progress. Underperformance, on the other hand, can result in bank failure and a crisis, both of which have negative consequences for economic growth. The purpose of this study was to see how the loan syndication factors affected the financial performance of Kenyan commercial banks. The specific goal of this study was to assess the impact of legal and regulatory environment on commercial banks' financial performance in Kenya. The study used a descriptive survey design to attain its goal. The study's goal was to take a census of all 39 commercial banks that had been open for at least a year. A self-administered questionnaire was employed in each bank to collect data from the 78 respondents, who were credit and operations directors. A multiple regression analysis was used to examine the impact of loan syndication parameters on commercial banks' financial performance in Kenya. Modern intermediation theory, Modern portfolio theory, and Loanable fund theory were among the theories that guided this research. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data. The study found that loan legal and regulatory environment has a statistically significant positive impact on commercial banks' financial performance in Kenya. The study recommends that bank's management should establish a specific unit to handle legal and regulation environment management in order to cope with credit rationing in the bank. This research adds to closing the knowledge gap on loan syndication and commercial bank financial performance in Kenya.

Keywords: *Legal and Regulatory Environment Factor, Loan Syndication, Financial Performance*

1. Introduction

In most countries around the world, commercial banks play a significant role in economic growth and development. One of these responsibilities is to act as a go-between for lenders and borrowers of monies (Oduro, Asiedu & Gadzo, 2019). These banks serve critical roles in the allocation of economic resources since they control a major portion of the money supply in circulation, promote liquidity, and ensure the smooth operation of the financial system (Udom & Onyekachi, 2018). They play an important role in economic growth and industrialization by moving funds from surplus units (depositors) to deficit units (borrowers), profiting from the spread (the positive difference between the interest received and interest paid) of the various interest rates charged (Aldeehani, 2019).

Commercial banks are constantly channeling monies received from depositors to those investors who require funding for investments (Sporta, 2018). They can do so if they can generate enough revenue to pay the operational costs they will incur over time. In other words, banks must have great financial performance in order to maintain their intermediation function. (2019).

The bank has numerous funding methods, one of which is loan syndication, which is utilized by commercial banks to mobilize capital to borrowers for favorable returns (Bruche, Malherbe & Meisenzahl, 2017). The term "loan syndication" refers to numerous banks issuing loans together (lenders). It is a procedure in which a group

of banks, at least two, create a loan and so make cash available to a single or multiple borrowing firms (Bos, Contreras & Kleimeier, 2016). Banks diversify their risk, share knowledge and talents, and can more easily meet capital limits by creating a syndicate (Chantal, Namusonge & Shukla, 2018). Participants in a syndicate can exploit one other's abilities to reduce knowledge asymmetries throughout the loan arrangement process. To eliminate double labor and lower each arranger's effort expenses, diverse duties and different types of expertise might be distributed across lead arrangers in a syndicate (Gao & Jang, 2018). Regulatory environment, information asymmetry, a bank's capital strength, liquidity restrictions, loan portfolio diversification opportunities, and loan maturity period are all factors that encourage banks to participate in loan syndication (Burzynska, Quyen & Contreras, 2017).

During the full year of 2016, global syndicated loans totaled US\$4.0 trillion, down 10% from the previous year and the worst year for global lending since 2012. (Slocombe, 2017). Similarly, loan syndication has developed in African countries, such as Nigeria, where it began in the 1960s when a group of commercial banks and acceptance houses bought trade bills for marketing boards as part of the generated bill finance scheme (Okonkwo 2015). During the oil boom of the 1970s, when there was a need for adequate finance to fund industrialization plans, formalized loan syndication arose.

There are apparent pieces of evidence of loan syndication tactics by commercial banks in the Kenyan financial system in order to mobilize significant money for major projects. For example, in 2004, Airtel Kenya formally Celtel Kenya agreed for a Ksh. 6 billion syndicated loan refinancing. Standard Bank acted as the global advisor and facility arranger for this credit facility. Barclays Bank of Kenya Limited, Kenya Commercial Bank Limited, and Stanbic Bank Limited also participated as lead arrangers for the issue. The loan had a five-year maturity period (Loita Capital Partners International,[LCPI], 2019).

2. Research gap

The banking sector's performance is viewed as a reflection of the economy's economic activities. Commercial banks play an important part in economic growth and development in many countries throughout the world (Oduro et al., 2019). The banking industry's point of growth and development is an excellent mirror of the economy's development (Alemu & Aweke, 2017). Financial institutions (banks) in strong financial health provide assurance not only to their depositors, but also to their stakeholders and the economy as a whole. Assessment of the financial performance and improvement of commercial banks in the banking sector is an effective measure and indicator to check the soundness of economic activities of any Country (Aspal, Dhawan & Nazneen, 2019).

Published investigations on loan syndication include Echekeba, (2015), who found that syndicate lending is a potent source of finance for big-time industrialists, Howcrofta et al., (2014), who discovered that syndicated lending was used to improve the returns and credit quality of the bank's loan portfolios, and Mekonnen, (2011), who discovered that lending limit and liquidity positively influences the possibility of syndicate lending in Ethiopian banking. Even though several Kenyan financial markets have begun to embrace loan syndication mechanisms, little is known in Kenya about the impact of loan syndication determinants on commercial bank financial performance.

2.1 : General Objective of the study

The general purpose of this study research was to determine the influence of legal and regulatory environment factor on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya

2.1.1: Specific Objective of the study

a) To establish the influence of legal and regulation environment on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya;

2.2: Hypothesis testing

H₀₁: Legal and regulation environment has no significant influence on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya;

3. Methodology

Since the choice of research philosophy is dependent on a research hypothesis to be investigated, positivism was determined to be the best acceptable method for this study. Positivism is based on the idea that reality is steady and can be viewed and described objectively without interfering with phenomena (Cresswell, 2008). This study employed a mixed research methodology that included both descriptive and correlational research approaches to evaluate the impact of legal and regulatory environment elements on commercial bank financial performance in Kenya. Credit directors (managers) and operation directors (managers) from each of the commercial banks were among the target respondents. As a result, there were 78 potential respondents in the target population. Primary and secondary data were used in this investigation. Creating a questionnaire was part of the data collection process. The total number of questions in the final questionnaire was 78 after analyzing and rearranging the surveys banks that deal with commerce.

The data in this study was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. Over the sample period, the mean standard deviation and different percentiles of the dependent variable (financial performance) were determined for all of the banks. For the 39 commercial banks from the independent variable, an inferential test was done for each significant variable to see if there was a link between the legal and regulatory framework and commercial bank financial performance in Kenya.

4. Study Results

4.1 Response rate

The respondents completed and returned 74 questionnaires out of 78, respectively. This indicates that 95% of the people responded. According to Kothari and Gard (2014), any response rate of 50% or more is sufficient for data analysis. Those that completed their questionnaires and returned them for examination were subjected to additional scrutiny. According to the study's findings, 37 of the 74 people who completed and returned their questionnaires for analysis were in charge of operations, while the remainders were in charge of credit. This means that 50% (37) of the respondents who successfully completed and returned their questionnaires for analysis were operation directors while 50% (37) were Credit directors.

Table 1 Response Rate

Respondents	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Questionnaires issued	78	100
Questionnaires returned	74	95
Questionnaires not returned	04	05

4.2: Reliability Test

A pilot study was carried out to determine the reliability of the questionnaires using 14 respondents. Reliability analysis was subsequently done using Cronbach's Alpha which measures the internal consistency by establishing if certain items within a scale measure the same construct. The findings were as summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Reliability Analysis

Statements	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
Legal and regulation environment	0.779	
Financial performance	0.860	

Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha in the table 2 reveals that financial performance had reliability of a value ($\alpha=0.860$), legal and regulatory environment had a value of ($\alpha=0.779$). This demonstrates that all the two

scales were reliable as their reliability values exceeded the prescribed threshold of 0.60, which is considered acceptable. According to Cronbach's Alpha reliability, a coefficient of 0.60 and above is considered "acceptable" in most social science research situations (Manerikar and Manerikar, 2015).

4.3: Financial Performance and Loan Syndication

4.3.1 Legal and Statutory Environment

The legal and regulatory environment comprises of those procedures required by commercial banks to adhere to before embarking on loan syndicate practices.

Table 3 *Legal and Statutory Environment*

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Rank
Credit limits enforced by bank regulators on loan syndication affects financial performance of your bank	74	3.473	.87934	4
The restrictions by national authorities on the extent banks can engage in income generating activities affects banks performance	74	4.027	1.39444	3
Conformity with the stock exchange regulations influences loan syndication (lending sharing) and influences commercial banks performance in Kenya	74	3.094	1.61473	5
The level of core capital influences banks decision to participate in loan syndication for better returns	74	4.270	.94067	1
The extent of the supervisory authorities power to take specific actions against banks affects their decisions to participate in loan syndication and this impacts on banks	74	4.229	1.04091	2
Grand average	74	3.818	.81235	

The result in Table 3 shows that most of the respondents indicated that there is a strong influence of Legal and regulatory environment factor in loan syndication on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya with the aspect of Credit limits enforced by bank regulators on loan syndication affects financial performance of your bank scoring a mean score of 3.473. The restrictions by national authorities on the extent banks can engage in income generating activities affects banks performance scoring a mean of 4.027, Conformity with the stock exchange regulations influences loan syndication (lending sharing) and influences commercial banks performance in Kenya scoring a mean of 3.094, The level of core capital influences banks decision to participate in loan syndication (lending sharing) scoring a mean of 4.270 and the extent of the supervisory authorities power to take specific actions against banks affects their decisions to participate in loan syndication and this impacts on banks scoring a mean of 4.229. Grand average of legal and regulatory scored a mean of 3.818, a score which is well above average meaning that changes made on loan syndication regulations influence the decision to syndicate.

The characteristics of core capital that influence banks' willingness to participate in loan syndication for greater returns earned the highest mean, meaning that any enforcement of credit limits by bank regulators is sensitive to the credit mechanism, and credit managers should pay particular attention to this. Cornelissen and Burzynska (2016) pointed out that a bank that is confined in its capital-to-asset ratio due to regulatory restrictions may be hesitant to reduce the ratio by putting a big bilateral loan on its balance sheet, preferring instead to syndicate a portion of the loan. By using the syndication technique, banks facing capital or liquidity constraints can continue to service the borrowing needs of an essential client without having to undertake the entire loan.

4.4 Finance performance

The financial performance involved verifying performance indicators ROA (measured by net income to total assets) and ROE (measured by net income to total capital or shareholders' funds). The result regarding banks performance is shown in table 4.

Table 4 Financial Performance

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
Net income to total assets for the year ended 2012	74	3.770	1.02766
Net income to total assets for the year ended 2013	74	3.500	1.21914
Net income to total assets for the year ended 2014	74	3.513	1.23655
Net income to total assets for the year ended 2015	74	3.297	1.30587
Net income to total assets for the year ended 2016	74	3.243	1.34194
Net income to total capital for the year ended 2012	74	3.676	1.02179
Net income to total capital for the year ended 2013	74	3.635	1.18112
Net income to total capital for the year ended 2014	74	3.595	1.28824
Net income to total capital for the year ended 2015	74	3.405	1.30253
Net income to total capital for the year ended 2016	74	3.311	1.39391
Overall average	74	3.495	1.23188

The influence of loan syndication factors on financial performance indicates that there is a strong influence of loan syndication factors on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. This is shown by the financial performance (net income to total assets) in the year 2012 with a mean of 3.770, 2013 with a mean of 3.500, 2014 a mean of 3.513, 2015 a mean of 3.297 while 2016 had a mean of 3.243. The results for net income to total assets in the year 2012 indicated a mean of 3.676, 2013 indicated a mean of 3.635, 2014 a mean of 3.595, 2015 - a mean of 3.405 while 2016 had a mean of 3.311. From the findings, it can be noted that the year 2012 recorded the highest value for the ROA (net income to total assets) as shown by a mean of value of 3.770 while the year 2016 recorded the lowest value for the ROA (net income to total assets) as shown by a mean value of 3.243. From the findings, it was also noted that the year 2012 recorded the highest value for the ROE (net income to total capital) as shown by a mean of value of 3.676 while the year 2016 recorded the lowest value for the ROE (net income to total capital) as shown by a mean value of 3.311. In addition, the values for standard deviation depict variability in the ROA (net income to total assets) during the five-year period with the highest deviation of 1.34194 in the year 2016 and the lowest 1.02766 in the year 2012. Further, the values for standard deviation depict variability in the ROE (net income to total capital) during the five-year period with the highest deviation of 1.39391 in the year 2016 and the lowest 1.02179 in the year 2012.

Overall the financial performance for the five years was a mean of 3.495 showing that performance of commercial banks in Kenya are satisfactory and therefore the management should come up with appropriate financial innovations that can enable them to maintain and improve on their performance. This agrees with the finding of Thiongo (2016) whose study covered a five-year period from 2011 to 2015 on the effect of growth in loan portfolio on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya and found that loan factors had an influence on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya.

4.4. Regression Analysis and Hypothesis Testing

The test of the hypothesis was performed and the results presented on the influence of legal and regulation on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya;

Table 5 Linear regression of legal and regulation and performance

<i>Model Summary</i>					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
	.599 ^a	.359	.350	.589	
<i>Coefficients^a</i>					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.759	.247		7.113	.000
Legal & regulation environment	.438	.069	.599	6.345	.000

The result in Table 5 revealed that legal and regulatory environment (X_2) explains 35.9% of the total variations in the financial performance of the commercial banks in Kenya (adjusted $R^2 = .359$).

The coefficients in the regression model indicates that legal and regulatory environment (X_1) will always exist at a certain minimum ($\beta_0 = 1.759$, $P=0.000$). The legal and regulatory environment (X_1) has significant influence on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya ($\beta_1 = .438$, $P = .000$). This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_{01}) and the acceptance of alternative hypothesis (H_{A1}). The study, therefore, concludes that legal and regulatory environment has a significant positive relationship influence on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya

5 Conclusions of the study

The main purpose of this study was to establish the influence of legal and regulatory environment on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. The data for the study was collected from 39 commercial banks using a structured self-administered questionnaire with five-point Likert-type scale questions. The target population for the study was all the 39 banks operating in Kenya. Most importantly, the study established that majority of the respondents generally agreed that there is an influence of legal and regulatory environment on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya.

5.1 Legal and regulatory environment and Financial Performance

The coefficients in the regression model indicate that Legal and regulatory environment will always exist at a certain minimum ($\beta_0 = 0.1.759$, $P=0.000$). The Legal and regulatory environment has a significant influence on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya ($\beta_1 = .438$, $P = .000$). This result concurs with Cornelissen and Burzynska, (2016) who pointed out that a bank which finds it constrained in its capital-to-asset ratio, because of regulatory requirements, could be reluctant to lower the ratio by putting a large bilateral loan on its balance sheet and may choose instead to syndicate a portion of the loan.

5.2 Recommendations of the study

Based on the study findings, it is important for the Kenyan government and regulatory authority to monitor the syndicated lending activity of banks. However, monitoring and regulating syndicated lending poses a significant challenge for the government and regulatory authority as loans are generally originated outside their regulatory sphere. This study research, therefore, recommends a collaborative effort displayed both by local government and regulatory authority and international authorities to regulate the syndicated loan market and control the possible excessive risk-taking behavior.

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